

As predicted, animal protein containing biologics induce de novo autoimmune disorders

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Regarding the following article in Medpage Today:

Biologics Tied to New-Onset IBD and Other Autoimmune Events

- Though mechanism is unclear, patients need monitoring for de novo disorders

<https://www.medpagetoday.com/reading-room/aga/lower-gi/82657>

They quote: "We don't really understand the mechanism behind this yet, and the effect might apply to agents other than etanercept," Korzenik told the *Reading Room*

It is absolutely ridiculous for people to claim that the mechanism is “unclear” or not understood. I predicted that animal protein containing biologics would induce de novo autoimmune disorders (1). Most biologics are produced using Chinese Hamster Ovary (CHO) cells. All biologics thus contain residual CHO host cell proteins. We have described the exact immunological mechanism involved in the induction of autoimmunity by immunization with homologous xenogeneic antigens (2). Bailey-Kellog et al. developed CHOPPI specifically because induction of autoimmunity by residual host cell proteins is a known problem (3).

Autoimmune disorders induced by biologics represent the second wave of iatrogenic diseases.

The first wave of iatrogenic diseases are of course all the autoimmune disorders induced by animal protein containing vaccines (1,4–9). The biologics that are now prescribed to “treat” these vaccine induced disorders are creating their own disaster, exactly as predicted.

For laypersons:

<https://www.verywellhealth.com/what-is-an-autoimmune-disease-189661>

Says: “You may be wondering how an autoimmune reaction can occur. The autoimmune reaction may be triggered: ... If **a foreign substance that is similar to a normal body substance enters the body.**”

Animal proteins and some plant proteins are very similar to human proteins. So injecting animal and plant protein containing vaccines or biologics is the definition of “**a foreign substance that is similar to a normal body substance enters the body**”.

Predictably, we have an explosion of autoimmune disorders due to this insanity of injecting animal and plant proteins into humans.

Specifically, chick GAD65 in vaccines cause type 1 diabetes (T1D) (1,2,10).

Bovine insulin (a cow’s milk protein) in vaccines cause T1D (11).

Bovine folate receptor alpha (a cow’s milk protein) in vaccines cause autism (12).

Animal/plant aquaporin-4 containing vaccines cause neuromyelitis optica spectrum disorders (NMOSD) (8).

Animal acetylcholine receptor protein containing vaccines cause myasthenia gravis (6).
The list is endless.

Immediate action is required to clean up all vaccines and biologics by removing all non-target antigens, using technologies such as affinity chromatography (13).

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